

WORKSHOP #2

Marine litter produced on board

Workshop Brief

The second participatory workshop is entitled 'Marine litter produced on board' and aims to raise awareness about the marine litter produced on board by the fishing vessels, its proper management and to foster behavioural change towards the adoption of best practices. The specific objectives of the workshop are to:

- Educate and raise awareness among participants regarding the importance of tackling marine litter issues and implementing on-board best practices.
- Identify common items of marine litter generated on board (e.g., old gear, fish containers, oils).
- Engage participants in defining effective on-board practices for managing the marine litter produced.
- Gather suggestions on how to disseminate information and encourage other fishers to adopt similar practices.

This workshop involves informative and hands-on exercises and will take approximately two hours (see the proposed agenda).

Workshop development

Registration

The registration team welcome the participants and hand them the Participant Information Sheet, two Informed Consent Forms, and the Feedback Form. Participants are asked to sign the presence list and return the signed informed consent form (each participant should keep a copy for themselves).

Welcome (*plenary*)

| 10 minutes

Participants are welcomed, followed by a quick presentation of the objectives and the activities planned for the workshop. The participants will randomly be divided into small groups, with a maximum of six elements.

Exercise 1: Litter classification (*group*)

| 20 minutes

Participants in each group start by nominating a spokesperson to present the results at the plenary sessions. Then, participants are asked to classify various litter items, represented by

images on printed cards, as litter or non-litter by placing each item in the corresponding section on the exercise sheet (Figure 1). Once a consensus is reached, participants write the name of each item in the appropriate column, to be presented in the plenary session.

Exercise 1: Classify each item as litter or non-litter

NON-LITTER	LITTER

NETTAG+ Exercise 1 | Group _____
Workshop #2 'Marine litter produced on board' | [add the location of the workshop] . [dd/mm/yyyy]

Figure 1. Example of the first exercise sheet (workshop #2)

Exercise 2: Litter destination (group)

| 20 minutes

The second exercise is divided into two parts and aims to identify the destination of litter items (identified in the previous exercise), based on participants' fishing experience.

In the first part of the exercise (Exercise 2A), participants are asked to distinguish between litter items thrown overboard and litter brought to shore. Once a consensus is reached, participants write the name of each item in the appropriate column on the exercise sheet (Figure 2), to be presented in the plenary session.

In the second part of the exercise (Exercise 2B), participants are asked to identify the ultimate destination of litter items brought to shore. Litter items previously identified as 'Bring to shore' should be allocated to one of the following destinations: i) stays on port, ii) deposited in a general garbage container, or iii) sent for recycling. Once a consensus is reached, participants write the name of each item in the appropriate column of the exercise sheet (Figure 3), to be presented in the plenary session.

Exercise 2A: Based on your own experience, identify the destination of each litter item

THROW OVERBOARD	BRING TO SHORE

Exercise 2A | Group
Workshop #1 'Marine litter produced on board' | *[add the location of the workshop]* . [dd/mm/yyyy]

Figure 2. Example of the sheet for exercise 2A (workshop #2)

Exercise 2B: Based on your own experience, identify the destination of each litter item that is brought to shore

STAYS ON PORT	GENERAL GARBAGE CONTAINER	RECYCLING

Exercise 2B | Group
Workshop #1 'Marine litter produced on board' | *[add the location of the workshop]* . [dd/mm/yyyy]

Figure 3. Example of the sheet for exercise 2B (workshop #2)

Presentation of results & discussion (*plenary*)

| 20 minutes

Following the initial two exercises, participants convene in the plenary session to share and deliberate on the outcomes. Each group's spokesperson displays the exercise sheets and presents the group's findings. A discussion among participants regarding the chosen destination for litter is encouraged (e.g. which items were not properly classified as litter/non-litter; was the destination most accurate? why wasn't litter separated for recycling?). At the end, the moderators present the correct results, fostering a reassessment of the initial evaluations.

Exercise 3: Further actions and dissemination (*group*)

| 20 minutes

Back on groups, and based on previous discussions, participants are asked to give suggestions to reduce the marine litter produced on board and select measures to be implemented on board and at ports. Then, they are asked to identify internal and external factors that can influence the success of the proposed measures through a SWOT analysis. After reaching consensus, participants write their suggestions on the exercise sheet (Figure 4).

General guidelines to explain the SWOT analysis to fishers:

- **Strengths:** Things that fishers are really good at or have an advantage (e.g. extensive knowledge of local marine ecosystems and fishing practices, strong sense of community and cooperation, a positive attitude and willingness to adopt new practices, adaptability).
- **Weaknesses:** Areas that need improvement (e.g. lack of awareness about new methods, difficulties in accessing information or financial resources, resistance to change).
- **Opportunities:** External factors or chances for positive developments in fishing practices (e.g. policies (e.g. EU Directive 2019/883) and subsidies that encourage and financially assist the adoption of better practices, advancements in technology such as efficient gear designs or waste management tools, market demand for eco-friendly practices, opportunities to enhance the community's reputation).
- **Threats:** External factors that could pose challenges or risks to fishing practices (e.g. lack of enforcement, lack of infrastructures, economic factors, environmental changes).

- Five exercise sheets per group (in A3 format) numbered with the practical exercise to be completed,
- Colourful pens.

In case partners decide to provide a theoretical background on the marine litter theme, the seminar slides corresponding to workshop 2 can be used.

WORKSHOP #2

Marine litter produced on board

Resources

2nd WORKSHOP

Marine litter produced on board

Agenda

Place | Date | Time

- | | |
|----------------------|--|
| 13:45 - 14:00 | Registration |
| 14:00 - 14:10 | Welcome |
| 14:10 - 14:30 | Exercise 1: Litter classification |
| 14:30 - 14:50 | Exercise 2: Litter destination |
| 14:50 - 15:10 | Presentation of results & discussion |
| 15:10 - 15:30 | Exercise 3: Further actions and dissemination |
| 15:30 - 15:50 | Presentation of results & discussion |
| 15:50 - 16:00 | Workshop final conclusions |
| 16:00 - 16:20 | Coffee break |

Feedback Form

We ask you to take a moment to provide your feedback on the workshop. Your responses will be used to improve future NETTAG+ workshops.

Name (optional): _____

On a scale of 1 to 4 where 1 is strongly disagree and 4 is strongly agree, please circle the most appropriate answer:

1. The Workshop venue was:

- | | | | | |
|--|---|---|---|---|
| a) Comfortable | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |
| b) Well located | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |
| c) Food and refreshments were adequate | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |

2. The Workshop content was:

- | | | | | |
|-----------------------|---|---|---|---|
| a) Relevant | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |
| b) Comprehensive | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |
| c) Easy to understand | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |

3. The Workshop was:

- | | | | | |
|--|---|---|---|---|
| a) Well paced | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |
| b) Breaks were sufficient | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |
| c) A good mix between listening and activities | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |

4. The facilitators were:

- | | | | | |
|--|---|---|---|---|
| a) Knowledgeable | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |
| b) Well-prepared | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |
| c) Responsive to participant's questions | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |

5. What did you like best about this Workshop?

6. What did you like least about this Workshop?

Thank you for participating, we appreciate your feedback.

Background information on marine litter

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101112812 (NETTAGPlus).

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA).

Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Indicate the place | indicate the date dd/mm/yyyy

TRANSPORT

the ocean is essential for marine transportation

CLIMATE REGULATION

covering 70% of the Earth's surface, helps to regulate the climate

> 50% O₂

AIR WE BREATHE

produces over half of the world's oxygen

CLIMATE REGULATION

covering 70% of the Earth's surface, helps to regulate the climate

BLUE ECONOMY

several billions euros are generated from the oceans

RECREATION

provides unique activities, such as fishing, surfing, diving,

FOOD

source of seafood, fish and essential ingredients

MEDICINE

many medical products come from the ocean

IMPORTANCE OF OUR OCEAN

Main ocean threats

PLASTIC/MARINE POLLUTION

14 LIFE BELOW WATER

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

1 NO POVERTY	2 ZERO HUNGER	3 GOOD HEALTH AND WELL-BEING	4 QUALITY EDUCATION	5 GENDER EQUALITY	6 CLEAN WATER AND SANITATION
7 AFFORDABLE AND CLEAN ENERGY	8 DECENT WORK AND ECONOMIC GROWTH	9 INDUSTRY, INNOVATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE	10 REDUCED INEQUALITIES	11 SUSTAINABLE CITIES AND COMMUNITIES	12 RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION
13 CLIMATE ACTION	14 LIFE BELOW WATER	15 LIFE ON LAND	16 PEACE, JUSTICE AND STRONG INSTITUTIONS	17 PARTNERSHIPS FOR THE GOALS	

UN, 2022: <https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/report/2022/img/info/Goal-14.pdf>

MARINE LITTER

EEA: <https://youtu.be/T7Cb44ab-YI>

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the European Union

What is marine litter?

“ Any persistent, manufactured or processed solid material discarded, disposed of or abandoned in the marine and coastal environment. ”

UNEP (1995)

- deliberately discarded into the sea, rivers or beaches
- brought indirectly to the sea with rivers, sewage, storm water or winds
- accidentally lost, including material lost at sea in bad weather (fishing gear, cargo)
- deliberately left by people on beaches and shores

Where does it come from?

20%
comes from the sea

- Lost shipping containers
- Lost/discharged maritime activities gear (e.g. fisheries, aquaculture, shipping, oil platforms, wind farms)

Ocean is the final destination of litter!

80%
comes from the land

Major causes are poor waste management and littering on land

- Litter dropped in cities, at the beach...
- Industrial waste discharges
- Litter blown by the wind
- Poorly managed landfills
- Microbeads from hygiene products
- Sewage related litter

Where does it go?

A significant amount of the marine litter is located at the sea bottom!

70% of marine litter is in the sea bottom

15% water surface and column

15% beaches and coastal waters

Funded by the European Union

Where does it go?

- Litter items can be transported across the seas and oceans over long distances by currents and gyres and accumulated in offshore 'garbage patch' areas
- The Great Pacific Garbage Patch is the best known
- It covers an estimated surface area of 1.6 million km² (3 times the size of France)

Watch [The Ocean Cleanup](https://theoceancleanup.com/great-pacific-garbage-patch/) video for more info:
[The Great Pacific Garbage Patch Explained](https://theoceancleanup.com/great-pacific-garbage-patch/)

1. North Pacific Gyre
2. Indian Ocean Gyre
3. South Pacific Gyre
4. South Atlantic Gyre
5. North Atlantic Gyre

<https://theoceancleanup.com/great-pacific-garbage-patch/>

What type of litter?

Data source (graph): [European Parliament](#), 2018

85% of land-based litter is plastic

Top 10 single-use plastic items

Addressed by the EU Directive 2019/904 on single-use plastics

Cotton buds

Beverage containers

Cutlery, straws and stirrers

Cigarette butts

Balloons and balloon sticks

Plastic bags

Food containers

Packets and wrappers

Cups for beverages

Wet wipes and sanitary items

Funded by
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Data source: European Commission, 2018
https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/plastics/single-use-plastics_en

Sources of plastics in the environment

The source

The primary source of marine litter is **mismanagement plastic waste**, which slowly leaks into the environment.

In 2018, it amounted to **3 million tonnes**.

Approximately **80% of marine litter starts on land**, while 20% begins at the sea.

How plastics spread to the environment?

Adapted from: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/media/infographics/sources-and-pathways-of-plastics/view>

Plastic litter in the sea

PLASTIC LITTER IN THE SEA

GLOBAL EMERGENCY

over 150 million tonnes
PLASTICS

1 tonne PLASTICS for every 3 tonnes FISH

PLASTICS more than FISH

WWF (2018). Out of the plastic trap saving the Mediterranean from plastic pollution

Microplastics

What are microplastics and where do they come from?

- Microplastics are tiny pieces of plastic material typically **smaller than 5 mm**
- Originate from degradation of larger plastic objects, such as plastic bags, bottles or fishing nets
- Directly released in the environment as small particles

European Parliament 2018. [Microplastics: sources, effects and solutions](#), accessed Nov. 2023

Based on <https://mp-1.itrcweb.org/environmental-distribution-fate-and-transport/#gsc.tab=0>

Plastics and microplastics

Some numbers in the marine environment

- Plastic waste enters the ocean at a rate of **11 million metric tons per year**
(The Pew Charitable Trusts and SYSTEMIQ, 2020)
- Over **200.000 tonnes** of plastic waste enters the Mediterranean Sea every year - a number that is expected to double if significant measures are not taken
(IUCN, 2020)
- Recent research estimates that at least **14.4 million tonnes of microplastics** have found its way to the bottom of the world's oceans
(Barrett *et al.*, 2020)

Plastics and microplastics

Impacts on the marine environment

Facilitate the spread of diseases or invasive species

Smothering the marine life
(preventing oxygen and nutrient flow and blocking light, reducing the number of organisms)

Entanglement of animals
(birds, fish, turtles and mammals in abandonment fishing gear and plastic packaging)

Microplastics **affect species living in bottom** environments and cause **ecosystem disruption**

Ingestion of plastic
(cause physiological stress, toxicological harm and starvation)

Harmful toxic effects
(plastics can contain many chemicals, some of which are hazardous)

Damage coral reefs
(deprive of oxygen and light, physical damage and increase risk of diseases)

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Based on UNEP 2021. Drowning in plastics

W2&W3

FISHERIES CONTRIBUTION TO MARINE LITTER

ROPES

significant source of microplastics (the older the rope the more microplastics released)

PAINT

paints and antifoulants contain toxic additives and release microplastics

A dark blue icon of a fishing hook and a net with fish inside.

LOST FISHING GEAR

lines, traps, nets lost by fishing activities into the sea

GARBAGE

produced on board and thrown overboard

LITTER FROM FISHERIES

LITTER PRODUCED ON BOARD

Litter produced on board

Litter produced on board

How long does it take to degrade?

NAPKINS
2-4 weeks

COTTON SHIRT
2-5 months

WOOL GLOVES
1 year

WOOL SOCKS
1-5 years

CIGARETTE BUTS
2-14 years

ALUMINIUM CAN
200 years

GLASS BOTTLES
undetermined

FOAM BUOY
50 years

BUOY FROM FISHING GEAR
80 years

HOOK
600 years

NYLON LINE
650 years

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Indicative numbers from different sources:
Safet4Sea; SRAM; Joly & Coulis, 2018; Futurism

PASSIVELY FISHED WASTE

Marine litter caught in fishing nets

1. Destroys fishing gear
2. Destroys the catch
3. Fishers lose time

€61.7 million/year
 Economic loss caused by marine litter to the EU fishing fleet

Marine litter caught in fishing nets

Economic impacts on the fishing sector

- Floating plastic debris can **affect the engine** cooling systems and become entangled in propellers
(Takehama, 1990; McIlgorm et al., 2011)
- Litter caught in fishing gears can be responsible for **damaging fishing gears, contaminating catch**, and even **damaging fishing vessels**
(Thomson *et al.*, 2004; Andrady, 2011)
- The total economic cost of this impact has been estimated to be nearly **€61.7** million in the European Union alone
(Mouat *et al.*, 2010; Acoleyen, 2014)
- The costs of removing litter from fishing nets, damage to catches, repairing gear, entangled propellers and obstructed cooling systems account between **1% and 5%** of fishers' revenue
(FAO, 2018)

LOST FISHING GEAR

Lost fishing gear

Abandoned, lost, or otherwise discarded fishing gear (ALDFG)

- ALDFG represent about **10%** of the plastic waste volume present in the oceans
(IUCN, 2021)
- That means somewhere between **500,000** and **1 million tonnes** of fishing gear gets left in the ocean every year
(WWF, 2020)
- Fisheries-related debris is the **largest single category** by volume found in beach litter
(UNEP, 2021)
- ALDFG can continue fishing for years (“ghost fishing”) with high impacts on marine ecosystems and consequently on fish stocks. Ghost gear is the **most deadly** form of marine plastic debris
(WWF, 2020)
- EU estimates that about **20%** of the fishing gear used in Europe is dispersed in the Mediterranean Sea, approximately **11,000 tons**
(INTEMARES, 2023)

ALDFG ecological and socioeconomic impacts

<p>Microplastics Plastic components of derelict gear break down into microplastic pieces, polluting the ocean</p>			
<p>Reduced Use Value of Coastal Areas Derelict gear can end up in nearshore habitats, reducing socioeconomic values of recreation, tourism, education and research, and negatively impacting residential and commercial use</p>			

Gilman *et al.*, 2023. Introduction to the Marine Policy special issue on abandoned, lost and discarded fishing gear

GHOST FISHING CYCLE

Adapted from www.bluetubebeach.org/blog/ghost-fishing/

OLIVE RIDLEY PROJECT

GHOST FISHING EXAMPLES

Projeto Tamar Brazil/Marine Photobank/Courtesy of World Animal Protection

© Emma Hedley

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© Brian J. Skerry - National Geographic Stock

© Shutterstock / VisionDive / WWF-Sweden

Causes of lost fishing gear

Direct causes

- Poor weather conditions
- Gear entangled on bottom (rocks)
- Conflict with fishing gear
- Shipwrecks and other artificial wrecks
- Vessel conflict with gear

Indirect causes

- Lack of disposal facilities
- Inaccessibility to disposal facilities
- Differentiated disposal facilities (oils, recycling)
- Expenses of disposal facilities

Adapted from [World Animal Protection](#) (accessed Nov. 2023) and UNEP, 2021

Lost fishing gear

NetTag project results (2019)

- **Fishing gear more frequently lost:** traps and small pieces of nets
- **Reasons for losing gear:** type of bottom, shipwrecks, adverse weather conditions, bad handling of the gear or interactions with other fishing gear
- **Hotspots for ALDFG:** fishing areas characterised by irregular bottoms (such as rocky bottoms, reefs, wrecks) or high hydrodynamic areas, up to 5-6 NM from the coast
- **Costs of retrieving lost gear:** a trawler vessel can spend between 5000€ to 12000€
- **Financial incentives to recycle fishing gear:** different national/local programs (not well-known by all fishers)

ALDFG reporting and retrieval

Why is important?

- When gear is lost it can often be retrieved if its location is known
- Understanding the extent, locations and causes of gear loss is key to developing effective prevention and mitigation strategies
- The **retrieval of lost gear is the only way to eliminate its negative impacts** (related to navigational safety, habitat or wildlife damage)
- For certain fishing gear like gillnets, prompt retrieval is most effective (delayed retrieval may lead to a loss of structural integrity, reduced fishing capacity, and is less effective in mitigating negative impacts)
- In case of traps and pots, delayed retrievals (conducted days or weeks after loss) can still effectively mitigate significant negative impacts on species

ALDFG | Gillnets

GILLNETS

- Gillnets are passive fishing gear, work as a "wall" resting in the water, catching fish that get gilled or entangled
- Highly susceptible to getting lost, often neglected due to its affordability and ease of replacement
- Continues catching fish after being lost, impacting the seabed even as it loses buoyancy
- Recommendations: Implement gear marking, explore alternative materials, and incentivise recovery efforts to minimise its environmental impact

WWF 2020. Ghost Gear Report

Likelihood of loss

VERY LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	VERY HIGH
1	2	3	4	5

Impact once lost

VERY LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	VERY HIGH
1	2	3	4	5

GGG, 2021. Best practice framework for management of fishing gear

ALDFG | Pots & Traps

POTS & TRAPS

- When lost, pots and traps continue attracting animals due to the lingering bait, creating a feedback loop with scavengers preying on trapped animals
- As this fishing gear is usually tied with a buoy, entanglements can still happen after traps/pots are destroyed
- Some countries enforce guidelines or regulations, making it mandatory to implement tracking mechanisms (gear marking or GPS) of devices

WWF 2020. Ghost Gear Report

Likelihood of loss

VERY LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	VERY HIGH
1	2	3	4	5

Impact once lost

VERY LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	VERY HIGH
1	2	3	4	5

GGG, 2021. Best practice framework for management of fishing gear

ALDFG | Fish Aggregation Devices

FADs

- Often constructed with netting from old purse seines, posing entanglement risks for fish and other animals around the FADs as well as predators that are attracted to the aggregations of prey species
- While many drifting FADs are tracked using satellite buoys, it is common practice to cease tracking drifting FADs, rather than recovering them, when they drift out of fishing areas
- When lost: continued entanglement of vulnerable species in FAD netting and rafts; and harmful impacts to marine and nearshore habitats of beached FADs

WWF 2020. Ghost Gear Report

Likelihood of loss

VERY LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	VERY HIGH
1	2	3	4	5
		Anchored		Drifting

Impact once lost

VERY LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	VERY HIGH
1	2	3	4	5

GGG, 2021. Best practice framework for management of fishing gear

ALDFG | Hooks & Lines

HOOKS & LINES

- Often discarded when damaged, as they can be quite cheap
- Longlines can span lengthy distances, but their impact when lost is less than other fishing gear, especially if deployed away from the surface
- However, baited hooks continue to catch fish, creating a feedback loop with larger predators preying on baited fish
- Mainline ropes attached to hooks are made from plastic-derived materials, posing entanglement risks to birds if close to the surface
- Curled turtle-safe hooks help mitigate sea turtle entrapment, reducing this specific impact

WWF 2020. Ghost Gear Report

Likelihood of loss

VERY LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	VERY HIGH
1	2	3	4	5

Impact once lost

VERY LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	VERY HIGH
1	2	3	4	5

Handline Longline

GGG, 2021. Best practice framework for management of fishing gear

ALDFG | Trawl nets

TRAWL NETS

- Expensive and fishers try to avoid losing them
- Often equipped with marking devices for tracking if lost, but entire net loss, necessary for tracking, is rare
- Near seabed trawling, especially in rocky areas, can lead to partial net loss, sinking and moving on the seabed
- Crumpled trawl netting on the seabed has limited chances of catching more fish but may entangle other species like crabs and affect the seabed through smothering
- Surface trawls, usually of polypropylene, can float if torn without weights or catch, having negative impacts similar to FADs

WWF 2020. Ghost Gear Report

Likelihood of loss

VERY LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	VERY HIGH
1	2	3	4	5

Mid-water Bottom

Impact once lost

VERY LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	VERY HIGH
1	2	3	4	5

Mid-water Bottom

GGG, 2021. Best practice framework for management of fishing gear

ALDFG | Purse seine nets

PURSE SEINE NETS

WWF 2020. Ghost Gear Report

Funded by
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- Segments of nets might unintentionally be lost if left on the working deck -> Dedicated containers for repair sections mitigate this risk
- Large segments of purse seine nets can cause similar harm on the sea surface as FADs and floating trawl segments
- Loss of entire nets is rare and intensive recovery efforts are made for lost nets due to their high economic value and replacement cost
- Lost weighted fishing nets likely sink to the seabed, posing entanglement risks for other animals if mesh size is small
- At the seabed, these nets may impact biodiversity or be moved around by bottom currents once the contained catch is degraded

Likelihood of loss

VERY LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	VERY HIGH
1	2	3	4	5

Impact once lost

VERY LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	VERY HIGH
1	2	3	4	5

GGG, 2021. Best practice framework for management of fishing gear

ACTIONS TO REDUCE PLASTIC POLLUTION FROM FISHERIES

Tackling sea-based marine litter sources

EU actions

- **EU Directive** 2019/883 on **port reception facilities** to tackle sea-based marine litter
- **EU Directive** 2019/904 on **single use plastic** products and **fishing gear** containing plastic
- One of the six main interim targets of the **Zero Pollution Action Plan** for 2030 is **reducing litter at sea by 50%**
- Council Regulation (EC) No 1224/2009 requires Union fishing vessels to have the equipment on board to **retrieve lost gear**

Directive 2019/883 on Port Reception Facilities

EU Directive for the delivery of waste from ships

- Aims to protect the marine environment by reducing discharges of waste from ships, and to improve efficiency of maritime operations in ports; ensuring that more waste is delivered on shore, in particular garbage, including waste from the fishing sector such as derelict fishing gear
- **100% INDIRECT FEE OBLIGATION** – allows the **FREE delivery of all litter** (including fishing gears and passively fished litter), up to the maximum dedicated storage capacity of the boat
- **GREEN-SHIP rebate** - fishing vessels should be encouraged to undertake certain measures (waste prevention and on-board waste management) to be eligible for a green-ship rebate

Tackling sea-based marine litter sources

Fishers are part of the solution!

- Delivery of waste to port reception facilities, including fishing gear waste
- Collecting and bringing passively fished waste ashore
- Retrieving or reporting lost fishing gear
- Recycling end-of-life fishing gear
- Participation on Clean-up Initiatives; Fishing for Litter

© NetTag project. Clean Ocean Day

Tackling sea-based marine litter sources

Fishers are part of the solution!

agenda-docapesca.weebly.com/noticias/a-pesca-por-um-mar-sem-lixo-na-ilha-da-culatra-e-em-aveiro

- All fishers have a bag or trash bin on board
- All boats have space on board to bring the waste produced back to land

How to reduce plastic waste?

Individual actions

use your own bottle

avoid unnecessary packaging

opt for fully recyclable packaging

bring your own lunch box

dispose of plastic recycling correctly

pick up litter & participate in beach clean-ups

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Based on [EUFIC](#) and [Safety4Sea](#)

Let's clean up the ocean together!

Thank you for your attention

www.nettagplus.eu

Follow @NetTagProject

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Workshop #2

A3 exercise sheets

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Exercise 1: Classify each item as litter or non-litter

NON-LITTER

LITTER

Exercise 1 | Group _____

Workshop #2 'Marine litter produced on board' | *[add the location of the workshop]* , *[dd/mm/yyyy]*

Exercise 2A: Based on your own experience, identify the destination of each litter item

THROW OVERBOARD

BRING TO SHORE

Exercise 2A | Group _____

Workshop #2 'Marine litter produced on board' | *[add the location of the workshop]* , *[dd/mm/yyyy]*

Exercise 2B: Based on your own experience, identify the destination of each litter item that is brought to shore

STAYS ON PORT

GENERAL GARBAGE
CONTAINER

RECYCLING

Exercise 2B | Group _____

Workshop #2 'Marine litter produced on board' | *[add the location of the workshop]* , *[dd/mm/yyyy]*

Workshop #2

Cards: marine litter

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Photo by Brian Yuraszts on Unsplash

PLASTIC BAG

PLASTIC BOTTLE

YOGURT PACKAGING

FREEPIK

ALUMINUM FOOD CONTAINER

FREEPIK

PLASTIC FOOD PACKAGE

FREEPIK

FOOD CONTAINER

FREEPIK

FRUIT WASTE

FREEPIK

CAN

Photo by Frank on Unsplash

GLASS BOTTLE

FREEPIK

TOILET PAPER

FREEPIK

FACIAL TISSUE

FREEPIK

ALUMINUM FOIL

FREEPIK

PLASTIC GLOVES

FREEPIK

RUBBER BOOTS

FREEPIK

CIGARETTE BUTTS

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CONTAINER

Photo by Mamon Lecuc on Unsplash

PLASTIC BOXES

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STYROFOAM BOXES

SCRAP METAL

BROKEN SMARTPHONE

BROKEN TELEVISION

OLD TIRES

WOOD

ROPE

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FISHING NETS

Lisa Sousa

FISHING POTS & TRAPS

FREEPIK

FISHING NET FLOATS

Lisa Sousa

FISHING MATERIAL

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STARFISH

Photo by Rosie Steggles on Unsplash

MACROALGAE

Photo by Tarpit Grover on Unsplash

SEABIRDS

Photo by NOAA on Unsplash

DOLPHINS

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SEA TURTLES